

On the capacity of Technical Debt to indicate security issues in open-source software products

George David Apostolidis¹, Miltiadis Siavvas¹, Ilias Kalouptsoglou¹, Dimitrios Tsoukalas¹, Alexander Chatzigeorgiou², Apostolos Ampatzoglou², Dionysios Kehagias¹, and Dimitrios Tzovaras¹

¹ Information Technologies Institute / Centre for Research and Technology Hellas, Thessaloniki, Greece

{geoapos, siavvasm, iliaskaloup, tsoukj, diok, Dimitrios.Tzovaras}@iti.gr

² University of Macedonia, Thessaloniki, Greece

{achat, a.ampatzoglou}@uom.edu.gr

Abstract. Technical Debt (TD) arises from insufficient design and poor coding practices, affecting important software quality attributes. As systems evolve, accumulated TD degrades code structure and increases maintenance complexity. However, poor code quality can potentially lead to the introduction of additional issues, including vulnerabilities. In this study, we examine the relationship between TD and software security across a broad sample of open-source Java projects, using a combination of static code analysis and statistical methods both at project- and at class- level of granularity. Two standalone TD and security assessment tools are employed to evaluate the selected source code artifacts regarding both their quality, measured in terms of TD, and their security level, expressed through a quantitative security score (i.e., the Security Index) and the number of the detected potential security issues. Statistical tests are then performed in order to to examine the existence of potential interrelation. The results of the analysis show that higher TD is associated with weaker security. Specifically, at project level, the high TD density and the Security Index of the studied projects were found to be negatively correlated, while at class level, high TD probability demonstrates a clear positive correlation with the number of security issues identified in each class, especially in specific vulnerability categories.

Keywords: Software Security · Software Quality · Technical Debt · Static Code Analysis · Correlation Analysis

1 Introduction

Technical Debt (TD) is an inevitable aspect of modern software development, often resulting from trade-offs between rapid delivery and code quality [1]. While TD is traditionally associated with maintainability and long-term development costs [2], it could potentially increase defect rates [3]. As systems grow in complexity and age, unresolved TD can degrade software structures potentially leading to the introduction of security risks, as well [4].

Open-source projects, which form a vital part of today’s software infrastructure, are particularly susceptible to the accumulation of TD [5]. The collaborative and often decentralized nature of open-source development, combined with the pressure for rapid feature delivery, often leads to short-term design compromises [5]. Over time, these compromises not only undermine code maintainability, but may also weaken the security posture of software systems [6].

Security is an important aspect of the Software Development Life-Cycle (SDLC) and requires special attention [7–9]. Recently, various research endeavors have attempted to link TD to security, either theoretically, such as through the concept of Security Debt [10], or empirically by conducting static analyses [11]. TD has been also used as an indicator for constructing Machine Learning (ML) models to predict internal security risk, showing promising results [5].

Despite the recent endeavors and the positive results, there is still a lot of work to be conducted to increase the confidence in these observations about the connection between TD and security. More specifically, current literature lacks a more fine-grained analysis of their interconnection. More specifically, their interconnection has not been fully explored both at project- and at class-level of granularity [12], while a comprehensive large-scale empirical evaluation and statistical analysis of this hypothesis is missing, as well. In addition, it remains unclear how TD correlates with specific security weaknesses (e.g., null pointer, resource handling, etc.)

To this end, in the present work we empirically examine the relationship between TD and software security based on a dataset of popular and widely-used open-source projects. In particular, 414 projects were retrieved from GitHub, comprising 783,486 classes, which were then statically analyzed with two individual tools for evaluating in a quantitative manner their TD and security level. Then, statistical analysis was conducted for uncovering correlations among quality and security, focusing both on project- and class-level of granularity. We also explored correlations among TD indicators and specific security issues. The analysis led to some interesting observations with respect to the relationship between TD and security of software products.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the previous work on the domain. Section 3 describes in detail the methodology of our research, while Section 4 presents our results. Finally, in Section 5, we summarize the conclusions of the analysis and provide suggestions for future work.

2 Related Work

In this section, we discuss previous works about the relationship of TD and software security aiming at providing a comprehensive view of how software quality and security can be jointly analyzed and managed. The relationship of TD and software security has recently started attracting the attention of the research community [4, 5, 13]. More specifically, recent work explores security issues as a consequence of high TD.

Rindell et al. [10] introduce the notion of Security TD (SecTD), arguing that security vulnerabilities, when unaddressed, should be treated as liabilities that accrue interest in the form of growing risk and maintenance costs. Izurieta et al. [13, 14] extend this view by connecting SecTD to specific software artifacts (e.g., architecture, code, testing, etc.), proposing remediation strategies that align with agile and DevSecOps practices.

The aforementioned studies are theoretical, attempting to transfer knowledge from the field of TD to the software security domain in a quite interesting way. Although the analysis and the mathematical modeling is strong and reasonable, they lack empirical evaluation, as well as empirical evidence for the potential relationship between TD and security in practice. Hence, another direction of research endeavors focus on empirically evaluating the relationship between TD and security, in an attempt to identify whether TD metrics could potentially be used as indicators of security risk in software.

Towards this direction, several approaches attempted to utilize software metrics (which are known TD indicators) as indicators of the existence of vulnerabilities in software artifacts [7]. Early efforts to link software quality metrics with security vulnerabilities focused on Complexity, Cohesion, and Coupling (CCC) metrics. Initially, Shin and Williams [11] as well as Chowdhury et al. [15] demonstrated in their studies that CCC could serve as early indicators of the existence of vulnerabilities in software systems. Subsequent studies [16, 17] leveraged statically extracted software metrics (e.g., Fan-in, Fan-out, Nesting Complexity, etc.) to build ML models capable of classifying PHP files to vulnerable or non-vulnerable.

Following this trend, subsequent studies started focusing on actual TD metrics and indicators, like code smells, code duplication, SQALE Index, etc., in order to investigate their potential connection with the security level of software products. For example, Siavvas et al. [3] conducted an analysis on 50 open-source projects at project-level of granularity, in which they assessed the relationship between TD and software security. Specifically, they observed a strong positive correlation between TD, expressed via SQALE Density [18], and software security, expressed through the Static Analysis Vulnerability Density (SAVD). In a follow-up study, Siavvas et al. [5] examined the ability of TD (particularly, TD metrics) to be used as the basis for building prediction models able to assess the internal security risk of software products, as well as the existence of vulnerabilities in software artifacts, leading to promising results. Finally, Gigante et al. [19] conducted a user study evaluating whether quality-oriented refactoring based on the results of SonarQube [20] can mitigate security flaws identified by Fortify [21]. While some overlap was observed, they found that security-specific remediation often requires targeted changes beyond those for code quality.

Although several research endeavors have examined the relationship between TD and software security, either theoretically or empirically, more work is required to reach safer conclusions on this aspect. Therefore, this study performs a deeper exploration of the relationship between TD and security. Not only a large dataset of Java projects has been collected, but also the dataset contains

information about TD and security factors both at project- and class-level of granularity, enabling a more fine-grained analysis. Specifically, in this study we do not build ML models based on software and TD-related metrics to predict security issues, but our focus is on identifying relationships and correlations among software quality-related measurements (i.e., TD Density and software quality metrics) and a quantitative software security score (i.e., Security Index). Moreover, our aim is to investigate the relationship between the probability that a class exhibits high levels of TD (high-TD) and the total number of security issues in the class. In addition, we examine how TD affects specific vulnerability types (e.g., resource handling, null pointer, etc.).

3 Research Methodology

In this section, we describe the methodology that we followed for examining the relationship between TD and Software Security in open-source projects. Our methodology is based on Static Code Analysis (SCA) and statistical analysis. The entire process is illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Overview of the research methodology of the study.

As depicted in Figure 1, we gather open-source repositories, and, after applying a filtering process, we analyze them through different SCA tools. Specifically, we have implemented a RESTful API that invokes two standalone tools, namely the Security Assessment Model (SAM) [22] and Technical Debt (TD) Classifier [23]. Under the hood, these tools rely on other SCA tools to perform their analysis. In particular, SAM uses the PMD analyzer [24], while TD Classifier employs CK [25], PMD’s Copy/Paste Detector (CPD) [26], and CLOC [27] tools and aggregates their results. In this way, a dataset of software projects along with information about their security issues, security level, and TD is collected. Subsequently, we perform a statistical analysis on the gathered information, both at project- and at class-level of granularity, and thus, we evaluate the relationship between software quality and software security. In the following sub-sections, more details are provided for each of the SAM, TD Classifier, data collection and statistical analysis steps.

3.1 Security Assessment Model

The Security Assessment Model (SAM) [22, 28] was developed as an hierarchical model that leverages low-level indicators to assess the internal security level of software systems. The process starts with extracting low-level indicators (i.e., security-related alerts) from the source code. The model then maps these findings to security properties (e.g. Resource Handling) and property scores are assigned using thresholds that have been empirically determined. These property-level scores are then combined to assess higher-level security attributes, the CIA triad (i.e., Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability). The Security Index (SI), a unified security score that ranges from 0 to 1 and represents the overall security of the examined software, is then created by the weighted average of these values. The internal structure of the proposed model is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Overview of SAM.

As can be seen by Figure 2 the model has a hierarchical structure. Four hierarchical layers make up the model’s general architecture: the measures, properties, characteristics, and overall security layer. The model starts with the low-level measures computed via static analysis and through several steps of aggregation, they compute the security score of the broader system, i.e., its *Security Index*.

The model specifies a set of 8 unique security properties that correspond to specific vulnerability categories, such as Null Pointer, Resource Handling, Exception Handling, etc., each of which has a corresponding code-level measure that directly determines it. The code-level measures that are used to measure those properties are actually the densities of static analysis alerts that belong to these properties, i.e., vulnerability categories/types. More specifically, the model employs the Static Analysis Vulnerability Density (SAVD), which quantifies security issues in relation to software size. SAVD enables a more fine-grained assessment of a system’s susceptibility to specific types of vulnerabilities. By standardizing vulnerability density across projects, SAVD facilitates consistent, system-level comparisons and insights. Considering $SAVD_i$ as the static analysis vulnerability density for the i -th vulnerability category, N_i the number of static analysis

alerts in category i , and LOC the total lines of code in the software product, SAVD is computed as:

$$\text{SAVD}_i = \frac{1000 \times N_i}{\text{LOC}}$$

Hence, for the purposes of the present analysis we focus on three different measures that are produced by SAM. These measures are: (i) the total Security Index of the analyzed project, (ii) the total number of security issues and densities that a project or a class contains, and (iii) the densities (SAVDs) of the various properties (i.e., specific vulnerability types). The first two measures facilitate project- and class-level analysis, whereas the third measure enables the conduction of more fine-grained analysis taking into consideration the type of the identified security issues.

3.2 Technical Debt Classifier

The Technical Debt Classifier (TD Classifier) was developed by Tsoukalas et al. [23] to automatically identify classes with high TD. To establish the foundation of their tool, in a prior empirical study [29], the authors empirically evaluated statistical and ML algorithms for their effectiveness in classifying software classes as having High or Not-High TD. To train the ML models, a dataset based on the study of Amanatidis et al. [30] was used. This dataset acts as an empirical benchmark of classes sharing similar levels of TD, based on the degree of agreement of three leading TD management tools (i.e., SonarQube, CAST, and Squore). By exploiting this dataset, the authors labeled the software classes belonging to the high-TD level as “high-TD,” whereas the rest of the classes were labeled as “not high-TD,” establishing in that way the “ground truth.” This way, a dataset of 18,857 classes was collected, with 1,283 classes considered as high-TD classes.

Furthermore, to facilitate accurate model building, Tsoukalas et al. [23] extended the initial dataset by adding metrics computed from various tools. Specifically, the CK Tool [25] computed structural code metrics, such as complexity and coupling. The CPD Tool [26] detected duplicated code blocks, which contribute to TD, while the CLOC Tool [27] measured size-related metrics, such as the total lines of code with and without comments.

Subsequently, Tsoukalas et al. [29] performed several data preprocessing steps, including outlier detection, missing values handling, oversampling, and a statistical analysis to discriminate metrics with predictive power. Moreover, they examined several ML models using cross-validation, identifying that Random Forest is the best-performing one, achieving an F_2 -score equal to 0.79%.

This Random Forest model constitutes the core of the TD Classifier tool. Moreover, the tool was developed in Python as a microservice exposed through a RESTful API. The backend is accompanied by a Mongo Database to store the results. The entire tool can be deployed as a Docker Container.

This tool plays an important role in the current study, allowing for the analysis of software classes with high levels of TD. In particular, by invoking TD Classifier, we managed to retrieve for each analyzed project the High Technical

Debt Density (HTD Density), which represents the percentage of classes with high TD in the analyzed project. Furthermore, we retrieved the High TD Probability (HTD Probability), which represents the probability for a class of the analyzed project to have high TD.

3.3 Data Collection

Using GitHub as our database and running both SAM and TD Classifier to retrieve specific quality and security measurements, we collected various open-source repositories written in Java. For the projects' selection, a filtering step was employed. More specifically, we ranked the Java projects that could be retrieved from GitHub based on their popularity (i.e., number of stars). Moreover, to ensure that the selected software projects are still actively developed, we included the additional requirement that the projects should have been updated in the last year (i.e., that they have received at least one commit during the past year). We also considered the filtering criterion that the selected project were long-lived (i.e., they are maintained for an extended period, potentially spanning years).

To automate the analysis of the selected projects with the TD Classifier and SAM tools, we implemented an additional tool that triggers the analyses and gathers those results that are necessary for the present study. The tool is implemented in Python as a RESTful API and can be deployed as a Docker Container. The findings of the tool can be stored in a MongoDB database.

Through this tooling, the study generated one dataset for project-level and one for class-level analysis. The former contains the results that were retrieved from TD Classifier and SAM at project-level of granularity. Overall, we retrieved the 500 most popular Java projects. From these projects, 414 were able to be analyzed by the two tools without errors or warnings. We decided to exclude those project that their analysis contained errors or warnings, in order to strengthen the reliability of the evaluation results of our empirical study.

Moreover, the class-level dataset contains the results of these tools for the individual classes of the analyzed projects. In particular, it contains 783,486 Java classes, providing detailed insights into metrics, such as High TD Probability (HTD Probability) and Total Security Issues in each class. Fragments of the project-level and class-level datasets are depicted in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively. For instance, we can see the values of Total Lines of Code (LOC), HTD Density, SI, Misused Functionality Issues, Null Pointer Issues, Coupling Between Objects (CBO), Weighted Methods per Class (WMC), and HTD Probability.

3.4 Statistical Analysis

Subsequently, the study conducts a statistical analysis to evaluate the relationship between TD and software security at project- and class- level of granularity.

Project-Level Statistical Analysis: More specifically, at project level, correlation analysis was employed in order to determine the interconnection between

Table 1. An example of key metrics for indicative Apache projects

Project	Total LOC	HTD Dens	Sec. Index	Misused Func.	Null Ptr	CBO	WMC
dubbo	372,350	0.0651	0.3013	0.0199	0.0013	12	40
kafka	942,167	0.1372	0.4012	0.0218	0.0010	33	68
incubator-seata	264,887	0.0569	0.5903	0.0080	0.0004	232	16,674
flink	2,268,660	0.1015	0.3527	0.0204	0.0018	23	45
skywalking	153,115	0.0400	0.4172	0.0442	0.0006	14	15

Table 2. Key metrics for indicative class files from different projects

File	LOC	HTD Proba	Total Issues	M. Func. Issues	NullPtr Issues	CBO	WMC
MockEngine.java	213	0.01	20	6	0	18	32
ListenerMap.java	319	0.51	44	4	0	8	28
MockRequestCycle.java	178	0.01	27	4	1	10	28
TestUrlValidator.java	120	0.02	0	0	0	3	11
TreeNodeView.java	399	0.24	83	9	5	22	58

metrics, such as the HTD Density and the SI. To determine the specific statistical test that we need to employ, normality tests were conducted to examine the distributional characteristics of the examined variables. For this purpose, we employed the Shapiro-Wilk test [31]. Specifically, HTD Density yielded a test statistic of 0.7784 (p-value < 0.05), and SI a test statistic of 0.9521 (p-value < 0.05). Considering as the null hypothesis that the distributions are normal, we can reject the null hypothesis for both variables, since both p-values fall below the significance threshold of 0.05.

Given this outcome, the Spearman rank correlation [32] was employed for the subsequent correlation analysis. As a non-parametric method, it does not rely on assumptions of normality and is well-suited for detecting monotonic relationships, in contrast to Pearson correlation that requires both variable to be normally distributed. In particular, Spearman analysis [32] was utilized to determine the correlation between TD and software security. To check the statistical significance of the computed correlation, we defined the following null hypothesis:

Ho: No statistically significant correlation is observed between TD and software security in project-level of granularity.

Then we tested the null hypothesis in the 95% confidence interval. More specifically, we repeated this analysis to investigate the correlation among the following indicators: (i) High Technical Debt Density (HTD Density) and Security Index (SI), (ii) HTD Density and security metrics, (iii) quality metrics and SI, and (iv) quality metrics and security metrics.

At this point, we have to clarify that, from now on, the term security metrics will refer to the densities of specific security issues. In other words, the density of a security issue is defined as the number of statically identified issues in a particular security category (e.g., null pointer) divided by the total lines of code in the analyzed project. These densities serve as indicators of the presence of specific types of vulnerabilities in the project [3, 33].

Class-Level Statistical Analysis: Similarly, at the class-level analysis, we employed correlation analysis to determine the relationship among TD-related and software security-related metrics in class-level of granularity. First, we conducted the Shapiro-Wilk test [31] to check whether the compared variables follow a normal distribution. The statistical test returned a test statistic of 0.545 (p-value < 0.05) for HTD Probability, which is the probability for a class to have high TD, and a test statistic of 0.071 (p-value < 0.05) for the Total Security Issues, which is the total number of statically identified security issues in the analyzed class. All computed p-values are by far lower than the 0.05 significance threshold, and therefore, we can reject the null hypothesis that the variables follow a normal distribution. Thus, we proceeded by using the Spearman rank correlation [32], which does not require normally distributed variables.

Specifically, we investigated potential correlation among the following indicators at the class level: (i) HTD Probability and Total Security Issues, (ii) HTD Probability and security metrics, (iii) quality metrics and Total Security Issues, and (iv) quality metrics and security metrics. To check the statistical significance of the computed correlations, the following hypothesis was tested in the 95% confidence interval based on the p-values of the Spearman correlation:

Ho: No statistically significant correlation is observed between TD and software security in class-level of granularity.

Strength of the Correlations: In both cases of project-level and class-level analysis, we used the guidelines provided by Cohen et al. [34] to judge the strength of the observed correlations. Cohen et al. rules suggest that a correlation among 0.1 and 0.3 is considered weak, between 0.3 and 0.5 is moderate, and above 0.5 is strong. Even a weak correlation is typically considered sufficient in the literature as evidence that a factor may have the potential to indicate security risks or the presence of vulnerabilities [11, 15, 35–37].

4 Results

In this section, we present the results of our study about the potential interconnection between TD and software security.

4.1 Results of the Project Level Analysis

At the project-level analysis, as described in Section 3, our aim is to investigate the relationship between HTD Density and SI, and between HTD Density and

security metrics. Furthermore, we aim at examining the correlation among various quality metrics and SI as well as among quality metrics and security metrics. Through this process we aim at observing potential relationships between quality and security indicators.

Figure 3 presents the results of the Spearman correlation between HTD Density and SI as well as between several quality metrics and SI. As regards the former, we can see that classes with HTD Density exhibit a weak negative correlation ($\rho = -0.277$), which is considered significant (p-value < 0.05). Therefore, we can state that the more classes with high TD the lower the security of the software projects, at least for the studied dataset.

Furthermore, Figure 3 shows that SI demonstrates varying degrees of negative correlation with several software quality metrics, indicating an inverse relationship between the security level of a software project and certain indicators of code quality. As shown in Figure 3, SI demonstrates a weak negative correlation with all the examined quality metrics, with the most notable examples being the following ones: Coupling Between Objects (CBO), Fan-out, Duplicated lines, Fan-in, Weighted Methods per Class (WMC), Response For a Class (RFC), and the size of the project expressed through the total of its lines. Elevated values in these metrics, typically indicative of higher complexity and tighter coupling, are associated with poorer security performance. This finding is in line with prior research endeavors, which also observed that there is a weak correlation between quality-related metrics and security [5, 11, 15, 35].

Fig. 3. Correlation of Security Index with Quality Metrics

Furthermore, Figure 4 provides an overview of how HTD Density correlates with various security-related metrics. We can see that, based on Cohen et al. [34], there is a moderate positive Spearman correlation between HTD Density and Null Pointer Density. There is also a weak positive correlation between HTD Density and the Resource Handling Density. Conversely, HTD Density demonstrates a negative correlation with the Misused Functionality Density, no correlation with the Logging Density, and very weak correlation with the

Densities of Synchronization, Assignment, and Exception Handling. Therefore, we can argue that there is a relationship between HTD Density and the existence of security issues of specific security categories. In particular, these findings show that high TD is more indicative of the Null Pointer and Resource Handling vulnerabilities and less so for the others.

Fig. 4. Correlation of HTD Density with Security Metrics

In addition, we examined the correlation among various quality-related metrics with security-related metrics. Table 3 presents the computed correlations using Spearman analysis. Through this analysis, we made some interesting observations about the potential interconnection of specific quality metrics with specific security metrics and, therefore, to specific vulnerability types.

Table 3. Spearman correlation between quality and security metrics at the project level. Significant correlations (p-value < 0.05) are marked with *. Text color denotes strength: black = very weak, blue = weak, green = moderate.

Metrics	sam_res	sam_assign	sam_excep	sam_mis	sam_sync	sam_null	sam_log
wmc	0.25*	0.05	-0.02*	-0.39*	0.06	0.41*	-0.03
dit	-0.01	-0.06	-0.06	-0.32	-0.09	0.29*	-0.12
rfc	0.12*	0.04	0.05	-0.26	0.17	0.19	0.04
ncloc	0.16*	-0.00	0.09	-0.28*	0.11*	0.35*	-0.06
total_lines	0.15*	-0.01	0.09	-0.26*	0.11*	0.34*	-0.06
fan-in	0.13*	0.01	-0.03	-0.33*	0.11*	0.40*	0.02
fan-out	0.00	0.04	0.04	-0.15*	0.13*	0.12*	-0.02
noc	-0.00	-0.02	0.03	-0.15*	-0.08	0.11*	-0.02
cbo	0.00	0.04	0.04	-0.15*	0.13*	0.12*	0.02
lcom	0.13*	-0.04	-0.09	-0.46*	-0.01	0.34*	-0.11*

As can be seen on Table 3, several quality metrics are correlated with security ones, some of which positively and some negatively. In particular, we can observe moderate positive correlation between quality metrics, such as Weighted Methods per Class (WMC), Fan-in, Non-Commented Lines of Code (NCLOC), total lines, Lack of Cohesion of Methods (LCOM), and Depth of Inheritance Tree (DIT) with Null Pointer Density. Considering both Figure 4 and Table 3, it

seems that Null Pointer issues are the most related ones with the high values of TD and high values of quality metrics in general. In contrast, there is a negative correlation of several quality metrics and Misused Functionality Density, similarly with the observation about the correlation of HTD Density and Misused Functionality Density (see Figure 4).

4.2 Results of the Class Level Analysis

At this section, we aim at identifying potential correlations among software quality and software security indicators at class-level of granularity. For this purpose, we focus on the HTD Probability retrieved from the TD Classifier and the Total Security Issues identified by SAM at class level, along with various quality and security-related metrics retrieved through static analysis.

Figure 5 illustrates the Spearman correlation between Total Security Issues and various software quality metrics. The plot reveals that, apart from Depth of Inheritance Tree (DIT), all the examined quality metrics are correlated positively with the Total Security Issues in a class. Nevertheless, the strongest positive correlations are observed with Weighted Methods per Class (WMC), Fan-in, and Max Nested Blocks, each exceeding a coefficient of 0.45. This suggests that classes with greater complexity, deeper nesting, greater method complexity, and increased coupling, are more prone to security-related issues.

Fig. 5. Correlation of Total Security Issues with Quality Metrics

Furthermore, Figure 6 presents the Spearman correlation between High Technical Debt Probability (HTD Probability) and a set of security-related metrics. We can see that all the examined security metrics are positively correlated with HTD Probability. Nonetheless, HTD Probability demonstrates stronger correlation with Assignment and Resource Handling issues, all exceeding $\rho = 0.30$ (i.e., moderate correlation). Moderate correlation exists also in relation to the total issues in a class. Therefore, we can argue that classes which are more prob-

able to have high TD are also more prone to vulnerabilities, and especially to vulnerabilities of Assignment and Resource Handling types.

Fig. 6. Correlation of HTD Probability with Security Metrics

In addition, Table 4 presents the Spearman correlation analysis on class-level among the examined quality and security metrics. In Table 4, **res_hand**, **assign**, **except**, **misused**, **sync**, **null**, and **log** columns stand for the densities of Resource Handling, Assignment, Exception Handling, Misused Functionality, Synchronization, Null Pointer, and Logging issues, respectively. Concisely, one can observe the significant correlation of software metrics, such as WMC, CBO, RFC, LCOM, Max Nested Blocks, Fanin, Fanout, Non-commented Lines of Code (NCLOC), total methods, total variables, and total lines with the densities of the different security-related metrics, with some metrics more and some less.

Most notably, there is a moderate positive correlation of WMC with Resource Handling and Assignment densities, RFC with Resource Handling, Max Nested Blocks with Resource Handling, Assignment, and Exception Handling, total variables with Resource Handling, Fanin with Assignment, NCLOC with Resource Handling, as well as total lines with Resource Handling. Therefore, it is clear that there is a relationship among most of software metrics and the densities mainly of Resource Handling and Assignment issues.

4.3 Threshold-based Analysis

Our analysis also revealed some deeper observations regarding the correlation between TD and software security under specific conditions (i.e., below/above specific thresholds). In particular, we calculated the median value of each examined metric after removing outliers, and then, we divided the dataset into two categories; one for values below the median and one for values above it.

Based on the threshold-based analysis, we created two groups of projects, namely the “low HTD Density” for those with HTD Density < 0.06 , and “high HTD Density” for those with HTD Density > 0.06 . We noticed in “low HTD

Table 4. Spearman correlation between quality metrics and security issues. Significant correlations (p-value < 0.05) marked with *, text color indicates strength: very weak, weak, moderate.

Metric	res_hand	assign	except	misused	sync	null	log
cbo	0.19*	0.15*	0.20*	-0.04*	0.15*	0.16*	0.14*
wmc	0.33*	0.35*	0.24*	0.05*	0.24*	0.29*	0.19*
dit	-0.01*	0.00	-0.01*	-0.04*	-0.04*	0.01*	-0.06*
rfc	0.31*	0.16*	0.26*	-0.11*	0.22*	0.21*	0.22*
lcom3	0.21*	0.22*	0.16*	0.13*	0.20*	0.20*	0.14*
npm	0.15*	0.21*	0.09*	0.05*	0.13*	0.18*	0.05*
total_methods	0.22*	0.24*	0.14*	0.02*	0.18*	0.23*	0.09*
max_nested_blocks	0.38*	0.36*	0.33*	0.09*	0.26*	0.28*	0.27*
total_variables	0.31*	0.17*	0.22*	-0.04*	0.21*	0.22*	0.20*
fanin	0.21*	0.40*	0.16*	0.23*	0.19*	0.21*	0.11*
fanout	0.19*	0.15*	0.20*	-0.04*	0.14*	0.16*	0.14*
noc	0.03*	0.04*	0.02*	-0.04*	0.04*	0.04*	0.02*
duplicated_lines	0.09*	0.01*	0.05*	-0.09*	0.03*	0.08*	0.04*
ncloc	0.31*	0.20*	0.24*	-0.05*	0.23*	0.26*	0.19*
total_lines	0.31*	0.19*	0.23*	-0.05*	0.23*	0.27*	0.18*

Density” the correlation between HTD Density and SI is moderately negative $\rho = -0.336$ (p-value < 0.05). In contrast, for projects with HTD Density ≥ 0.06 , the correlation weakened substantially $\rho = -0.064$ (p-value < 0.05), possibly due to a saturation effect, where, at higher levels of TD Density, other structural or contextual factors begin to play a more significant role.

Furthermore, in our class-level analysis, we observed that the relationship between total (security) issues and HTD Probability varies depending on class-level thresholds. Specifically, in classes exceeding the median value of 5 total issues, the relationship becomes substantially stronger, with a positive Spearman correlation of $\rho = 0.753$ (p-value < 0.05) in comparison with classes containing less than 5 issues $\rho = -0.178$ (p-value < 0.05).

5 Conclusion and Future Work

In this study the primary purpose was to investigate the potential relationship between TD and software security. To this end, we used static code analysis-based methods to collect information about the software quality and security of various open-source projects. We then employed a statistical analysis and were led to some interesting observations. In brief, the findings showed a statistically significant negative correlation between HTD Density and Security Index in project-level analysis, indicating that projects with more classes with high TD exhibit lower security level. Moreover, we observed a significant positive correlation between HTD Probability and total number of security issues in class-level analysis, especially in case of classes with more than 5 total issues.

Suggestions for further research include the investigation of potential causal links among TD variables and software security and how certain quality-related characteristics impact security. In addition, we could replicate the analysis using commercial software products and identify differences with the open-source ones.

Acknowledgements Work reported in this paper has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Program through the DOSS project, Grant Number 101120270.

References

1. Cunningham, W.: The wycash portfolio management system. In: OOPSLA Experience Reports. (1992)
2. Avgeriou, P., Bogdanov, C.A., Kruchten, M., Lago, P., Nord, R.: An overview and comparison of technical debt measurement tools. *IEEE Software* **38**(3) (2020)
3. Siavvas, M., Tsoukalas, D., Jankovic, M., Kehagias, D., Chatzigeorgiou, A., Tzouvaras, D., Anicic, N., Gelenbe, E.: An empirical evaluation of the relationship between technical debt and software security. In: *Empirical Analysis on Software Quality*. Springer (2019) To appear.
4. Rindell, K., Holvitie, J.: Security risk assessment and management as technical debt. In: *International Conference on Cyber Security and Protection of Digital Services (Cyber Security)*, IEEE (2019)
5. Siavvas, M., Tsoukalas, D., Jankovic, M., Kehagias, D., Tzouvaras, D.: Technical debt as an indicator of software security risk: A machine learning approach for software development enterprises. *Enterprise Information Systems* **16**(5) (2022)
6. Gkortzis, A., Mitropoulos, D., Spinellis, D.: Vulinoss: a dataset of security vulnerabilities in open-source systems. In: *Proceedings of the 15th International conference on mining software repositories*. (2018) 18–21
7. Kalouptsoglou, I., Siavvas, M., Ampatzoglou, A., Kehagias, D., Chatzigeorgiou, A.: Software vulnerability prediction: A systematic mapping study. *Information and Software Technology* **164** (2023)
8. Kelli, V., Radoglou-Grammatikis, P., Lagkas, T., Markakis, E.K., Sarigiannidis, P.: Risk analysis of dnp3 attacks. In: *2022 IEEE International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience (CSR)*. (2022) 351–356
9. Siganos, M., Radoglou-Grammatikis, P., Kotsiuba, I., Markakis, E., Moscholios, I., Goudos, S., Sarigiannidis, P.: Explainable ai-based intrusion detection in the internet of things. In: *Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Availability, Reliability and Security*. (2023) 1–10
10. Rindell, K., Holvitie, J., et al.: Managing security in software: Or: How i learned to stop worrying and manage the security technical debt. In: *Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Availability, Reliability and Security (ARES)*, ACM (2019)
11. Shin, Y., Williams, L.: An empirical model to predict security vulnerabilities using code complexity metrics. In: *Proceedings of the 2nd ACM-IEEE International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement (ESEM)*, ACM (2008)
12. Verendel, V.: Quantified security is a weak hypothesis: A critical survey. In: *Proceedings of the New Security Paradigms Workshop (NSPW)*, ACM (2009)
13. Izurieta, C., Rice, D., Kimball, K., Valentien, T.: A position study to investigate technical debt associated with security weaknesses. In: *Proceedings of the International Conference on Technical Debt (TechDebt)*, Gothenburg, Sweden, IEEE (2018)
14. Izurieta, C., Prouty, M.: Leveraging secdevops to tackle the technical debt associated with cybersecurity attack tactics. In: *Proceedings of the Second International*

- Conference on Technical Debt (TechDebt), Montreal, Quebec, Canada, IEEE Press (2019) 33–37
15. Chowdhury, I., Zulkernine, M.: Can complexity, coupling, and cohesion metrics be used as early indicators of vulnerabilities? In: Proceedings of the ACM Symposium on Applied Computing (SAC), ACM (2010)
 16. Walden, J., Stuckman, J., Scandariato, R.: Predicting vulnerable components: Software metrics vs text mining. In: IEEE 25th international symposium on software reliability engineering, IEEE (2014)
 17. Kalouptsoglou, I., Siavvas, M., Tsoukalas, D., Kehagias, D.: Cross-project vulnerability prediction based on software metrics and deep learning. In: International Conference on Computational Science and Its Applications, Springer (2020)
 18. Letouzey, J.L., Ilkiewicz, M.: Managing technical debt with the sqale method. *IEEE software* **29**(6) (2012) 44–51
 19. Gigante, D., Pecorelli, F., Barletta, V.S., Janes, A., Lenarduzzi, V., Taibi, D., Baldassarre, M.T.: Resolving security issues via quality-oriented refactoring: A user study. In: International Conference on Technical Debt, IEEE (2023)
 20. SonarSource. <https://www.sonarsource.com/products/sonarqube/> (2025)
 21. OpenText: Opentext static application security testing (fortify). <https://www.opentext.com/products/static-application-security-testing> (2025)
 22. Siavvas, M., Kehagias, D., Tzovaras, D., Gelenbe, E.: A hierarchical model for quantifying software security based on static analysis alerts and software metrics. *Software Quality Journal* **29**(2) (2021)
 23. Tsoukalas, D., Chatzigeorgiou, A., Ampatzoglou, A., Mittas, N., Kehagias, D.: Td classifier: Automatic identification of java classes with high technical debt. In: Proceedings of the International Conference on Technical Debt, IEEE (2022)
 24. PMD: Pmd source code analyzer. <https://pmd.github.io/> (2025)
 25. Aniche, M.: Java code metrics calculator (ck). <https://github.com/mauricioaniche/ck/> (2015)
 26. PMD Open Source Project: Finding duplicated code with cpd (2025)
 27. Danial, A.: Count Lines of Code cloc. <https://github.com/AlDanial/cloc#quick-start-> (2025)
 28. Siavvas, M.G., Chatzidimitriou, K.C., Symeonidis, A.L.: Qatch-an adaptive framework for software product quality assessment. *Expert Systems with Applications* **86** (2017) 350–366
 29. Tsoukalas, D., Mittas, N., Chatzigeorgiou, A., Kehagias, D., Ampatzoglou, A., Amanatidis, T., Angelis, L.: Machine learning for technical debt identification. *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering* **48**(12) (2021) 4892–4906
 30. Amanatidis, T., Ampatzoglou, A., Chatzigeorgiou, A., Avgeriou, P.: Evaluating the agreement among technical debt measurement tools: Building an empirical benchmark. *Empirical Software Engineering* **25**(5) (2020)
 31. Shapiro, S.S., Wilk, M.B.: An analysis of variance test for normality (complete samples). *Biometrika* **52**(3-4) (dec 1965)
 32. In: Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient. Springer New York (2008)
 33. Walden, J., Doyle, M.: Savi: Static-analysis vulnerability indicator. *IEEE Security & Privacy* **10**(3) (2012)
 34. Cohen, J.: Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences. Academic press (2013)
 35. Shin, Y., Williams, L.: Is complexity really the enemy of software security? In: Proceedings of the 4th ACM Workshop on Quality of Protection (QoP), Alexandria, Virginia, USA, Association for Computing Machinery (2008)

36. Camilo, F., Meneely, A., Nagappan, M.: Do bugs foreshadow vulnerabilities? a study of the chromium project. In: 2015 IEEE/ACM 12th Working Conference on Mining Software Repositories, IEEE (2015)
37. Moshtari, S., Sami, A.: Evaluating and comparing complexity, coupling and a new proposed set of coupling metrics in cross-project vulnerability prediction. In: Proceedings of the 31st annual ACM symposium on applied computing. (2016)

Appendix

This appendix outlines the alert-based properties (i.e., vulnerability categories) utilized in the proposed security assessment model, as described by [22]. For each property, the most representative Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE) identifier is also included. In addition, this appendix outlines the software metrics used in the analysis, as retrieved from CK, CPD, and CLOC tools.

Security Alert Categories

- **Null Pointer** : Identifies issues related to null pointer dereference, which can lead to critical failures such as system crashes. (**CWE-476**)
- **Assignment** : Targets insecure variable assignments and declarations, such as cases where local variables are not declared as final, increasing the risk of unauthorized manipulation.
- **Exception Handling** : Detects improper exception handling patterns that may result in program crashes or unintended information disclosure. (**CWE-388, CWE-199**)
- **Resource Handling** : Highlights mismanagement of system resources (e.g., memory, connections, etc.), which can cause performance degradation or denial-of-service conditions. (**CWE-399**)
- **Logging** : Examines poor logging practices. Inadequate logging may miss critical incidents, while excessive or misplaced logs (e.g., within loops) can affect performance. (**CWE-778**)
- **Adjustability** : Flags hard-coded, security-sensitive values in the code. If exposed, these values may be exploited by attackers. (**CWE-547**)
- **Misused Functionality** : Detects incorrect or insecure usage of language features or widely-used APIs that may violate expected behavior. (**CWE-227**)
- **Synchronization** : Identifies concurrency issues such as race conditions and deadlocks that can result in security vulnerabilities like unauthorized access or service unavailability. (**CWE-662**)

CK Metrics

- **CBO (Coupling Between Objects)**: Number of classes to which a given class is coupled. High coupling indicates less modularity.
- **WMC (Weighted Methods per Class)**: Sum of the complexities (or count) of methods in a class. A proxy for class complexity.

- **DIT (Depth of Inheritance Tree)**: Depth of the class in the inheritance hierarchy. Deeper trees may increase complexity.
- **RFC (Response For Class)**: Number of methods that can be invoked in response to a message to an object, including local and external.
- **LCOM (Lack of Cohesion of Methods)**: Measures how well the methods of a class are related through shared attributes. High values imply low cohesion.
- **LCOM3**: A variant of LCOM using an alternative formula to improve interpretation and stability.
- **NPM (Number of Public Methods)**: Number of public methods defined in a class.
- **Total Methods**: Total number of methods in a class, regardless of access level.
- **Max Nested Blocks**: Maximum depth of nested control structures within class methods (e.g., nested if/while/for blocks).
- **Total Variables**: Total number of variable declarations in a class (fields and locals).
- **Fan-in**: Number of methods or classes that call methods of the given class. Indicates reusability or dependency.
- **Fan-out**: Number of other classes used by the given class. A form of outgoing coupling.
- **NOC (Number of Children)**: Number of direct subclasses that inherit from a class.

CPD Metric

- **Duplicated Lines**: Number of lines of code that appear as duplicated blocks elsewhere in the codebase. High duplication increases maintenance effort and technical debt.

CLOC Metrics

- **Comment Lines**: Total number of comment lines, including inline and block comments. Indicates documentation quality.
- **NCLOC (Non-Commenting Lines of Code)**: Total lines of actual source code, excluding comments and blank lines.
- **Total Lines**: Total number of lines in the file, including comments, code, and blank lines.